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SOME FEATURES OF STATE REGULATION OF PENDULUM MIGRATIONS IN UKRAINE

Features and perspectives of state regulation of pendulum migration processes in Ukraine are analyzed. The main reasons for the emergence of these processes in the country are investigated. The principles are proposed, according to which it is advisable to implement state regulation of the pendulum migration and combine the interests of economically active citizens with the interests of the state.

Keywords: *state regulation, pendulum migration, economic activity.*

Проаналізовано особливості та перспективи державного регулювання маятниковими міграційними процесами в Україні. Досліджено основні причини виникнення в країні цих процесів. Запропоновано принципи, згідно яких доцільно здійснювати державне регулювання маятничковою міграцією і поєднувати інтереси економічно активних громадян з інтересами держави.

Ключові слова: державне регулювання, маятникова міграція, економічна активність.

Problem setting. It is generally accepted that pendulum migration is the regular movement of the population between a settlement of a place of residence and a place of work or study. Pendulum migration appears mainly because of the disparity between the location of production and the resettlement of people. Small towns can't boast of an abundance of job offers. This is due to many factors that contribute to the increasingly widespread migration process. Anyway, the size of the city, the specialization and its population by people are historically established indicators, which are difficult to be influenced from outside. They establish economic, political and social development on a certain path, which the city will follow in the future. However, most often it happens that only one or two sectors develop at full strength in a small city. In other areas, the dynamics of job creation lags far behind job offers, and existing vacancies do not attract citizens in terms of the nature of work, and more often - wages. This greatly narrows the circle of interesting vacancies in which a person could and would like to manifest himself [3]. In this regard, the development of mechanisms for state regulation of these processes is an important factor for the diversified development of the country as a whole.

Recent research and publication analysis. Many Ukrainian and foreign scientists paid attention to the problems of studying the processes of pendulum migration at different times. Among them there are such academic figures as O. A. Malinovskaya, O. V. Poznyak, E. S. Maltseva, I. V. Dubeyko, Yu. Ya. Voloshin, O. V. Kupets, Hein de Haas, V. Yulianna and others.

At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that the peculiarities and methodology of state management of the pendulum migration processes specifically in Ukraine require additional scientific research in connection with the insufficient number of such studies in the past, and consequently a small number of scientific publications in this field.

Paper objective. The purpose of our scientific publication is to study the peculiarities of pendulum migration in Ukraine, as well as to identify the prospects for state regulation of these processes. It is supposed to come up with the principles according to which state management of the pendulum migration processes should be carried out.

Paper main body. Ever since Ukraine embarked on the path of market relations, a persistent conviction has gradually emerged, which implies that in conditions of imperfect competition without state regulation it is impossible to ensure

social and economic development. One of the factors of sustainable development of society is labor, natural, human and social capital, or rather its full-fledged use. Raising the standard of living of the population leads to the fact that the quality of human capital and the level of social stability and security are increasing [4]. Today everyone in Ukraine is able to get education in accordance with their desires. A large number of higher educational institutions accept students for studying in the most diverse areas, not taking into account the level of demand for the profession in the labor market of the region, the average level of wages in the chosen area, and the readiness of a potential young specialist for territorial mobility.

Moving workers to a new place of residence together with the whole family may not be appropriate if the material and other costs of a change of residence, including the cost of buying or renting a home at the destination and severing ties, are too high compared to the expected benefits [5], as it often happens in Ukraine. Under these conditions, the pendulum labor migration becomes especially important. Such migration can only have positive economic effects (a decrease in unemployment and a rise in the well-being of families, a development of human capital and a rise in labor productivity, an increase in economic activity in migrants' origin areas), but also demographic and social effects, in particular a reduction in out-migration from villages and small towns in large cities and not narrow reproduction of the population because of the preservation of the model of an average child's family in smaller settlements.

The process of pendulum migration emerged and developed in the period of urbanization, when the gap between urban and rural cultures became the most pronounced. If earlier, before the growth in industrial cities, people in Ukraine were mostly engaged in subsistence farming, after the emergence of specialized devices and machines, labor productivity increased several times, and the need for human hands decreased. People in search of work began to travel to the nearest cities to feed their families. The role of the city in the development of society has increased. On the territory of a large part of the regions, especially in rural areas, the dynamics of job creation requiring specialists with higher education are significantly behind those in the labor market, while existing vacancies are not attractive enough for young economically active citizens in terms of the nature of the work, and first of all - a low level of wages. The imbalance of regional labor markets from the point of view of professional and qualitative conformity of supply and demand is a characteristic feature of certain regions of Ukraine. All this leads to the emergence of pendulum migration processes on the territory of the state.

In addition, significant growth in the volume of pendulum migration is facilitated by the following factors [1]:

- Ability to compile and submit a resume using the Internet;
- High level of transport infrastructure;
- A large number of unreliable information on employment, obtained not through state structures.

The main problem of studying this type of mobility of labor resources is that

it is very difficult to take into account the pendulum labor migrants.

In the domestic scientific literature only the fragmentary and outdated estimates of the number of domestic labor migrants are given, which do not give a complete picture of the dynamics of the number and composition of persons working outside of their settlement. Thus, according to a survey conducted in 2010, the number of pendulum labor migrants in the structure of employed persons was about 13.5% [2]. Taking into account the events, namely the military actions that have taken place in the eastern regions of Ukraine in recent years, as well as the annexation by the Russian Federation of the Crimean peninsula, it can be concluded that there is a tendency to increase the number of domestic labor migrants.

It is obvious that migration intentions are formed under the influence of a whole complex of various factors, one group of which is "pushing out," the other is "attracting." And in each case, this or that group of reasons prevails, depends both on the material well-being of the family, and on the level of the person's ambition, his desire for professional growth and self-improvement [6]. However, in modern conditions, it is common to distinguish three main factors affecting the person's decision on territorial mobility: unemployment, lack of vacancies in the specialty and low wages.

The choice of the most priority methods for regulating pendulum migration depends on one side - based on the interests of the individual in terms of respecting his rights and freedoms, on the other - from the priority tasks of socio-economic development of the region. It can be concluded that the pendulum migration movements are regulated by the action of market forces: the interaction of demand and supply. Relatively high level of wages in some regions and low in others (in conjunction with the lack of demand for employment in certain professions) lead to the displacement of the population from villages to the cities of the region and beyond. The emerging problems associated with this process are solved by potential and real pendulum labor migrants, usually alone. Constraints are practically absent or are not a priority.

Conclusions. So, the state regulation of the pendulum migration should begin with the definition of measures aimed at weakening the influence of "pushing out" factors and strengthening the "attractors".

The regulation of the pendulum labor migration should be based on the following principles:

- protection of human rights and freedoms on the basis of strict observance of the norms of constitutional law;
- combination of interests of the individual, region and state;
- development of the system of social partnership at all levels.

These principles will allow combining the interests of economically active citizens with the interests of the state and the tasks of socio-economic development of individual regions and Ukraine as a whole.

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**КОНЦЕПЦІЯ УНІФІКАЦІЇ ДЕРЖАВНИХ МЕХАНІЗМІВ ЩОДО
ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ СОЦІАЛЬНО-ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ БЕЗПЕКИ УКРАЇНИ**

**THE CONCEPT OF UNIFICATION OF STATE MECHANISMS
ON ENSURING SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SECURITY OF UKRAINE**